

Molecular discriminative binding behaviour of crosslinked polyvinylpyrrolidone with analogous dyes orange G and orange H

E. Subramanian*, R. Murugesan** and G. Anitha

Department of Chemistry, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627 012, India

E-mail : smanian2002@yahoo.com Fax : 91-462-2334363/2322973

Manuscript received 15 March 2002, revised 1 October 2002, accepted 23 May 2003

Two structurally analogous dyes Orange G (OG) and Orange II (OH) with slight difference in their molecular features (in the number and position of sulfonato groups) were studied for their binding to crosslinked polyvinylpyrrolidone (CPVP) in double-distilled water (pH \approx 5.5) and phosphate buffer (pH = 7.2) at different temperatures by batch adsorption technique. The binding data were analysed by Scatchard method and Giles adsorption isotherm. CPVP clearly exposed the differing molecular features of associating dyes through remarkable difference in binding plots. OG showed a lesser degree of binding than did OH in both the solvent media but the difference became small in buffer. Further, OG displayed a binding mode of mixed cooperativity with the likely formation of two succeeding complexes while OH sorbed with a simple positive cooperativity forming only one type of complex.

Molecular recognition involves the selective and usually non-covalent binding of a guest species to complementary host. Many studies are now devoted to enlighten this molecular process and also to the design and discovery of better hosts¹. For instance, the different binding regions in the protein bovine serum albumin have been recognised by two structurally similar dyes rose bengal and eosin blue². The different conformational characteristics of DNA and t-RNA have been ascertained in polymer-induced circular dichroism study with thiazine dyes³. The present work involves two dyes Orange G (OG, 1-phenylazo-2-naphthol-6,8-disulfonic acid; CI No. 16230) and Orange H [OH; 4-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylazo)benzenesulfonic acid; CI No. 15510], both being well-known staining agents in biology. They are analogous in all respects except in the number and position of sulfonato groups. Crosslinked polyvinylpyrrolidone (CPVP) is a functional polymer in pharmaceuticals as tablet-disintegrant⁴, binder and release-control agent⁵. In our previous studies^{6,7} we investigated the crucial role of sorbed water in the uptake of ligands by this polymer gel. Our recent study⁸ gave some information on molecular features of ligands (drug and drug analogues of phenyl and naphthyl derivatives) to get bound to CPVP. The present study is to investigate whether CPVP is able to discriminate in binding the slight different molecular features of OG and OH, akin to the molecular recognisable binding mode of biopolymers towards their ligands.

Results and discussion

Binding plots :

Fig. 1a shows the Scatchard plots⁹ for both the systems in double-distilled water. OG exhibits more or less a V shaped biphasic plot while OH results in a simple linear upward plot. In phosphate buffer, however, they produce Scatchard plots of diametrically opposite trend but still in discriminative features. OG shows initially convex but subsequently linear Scatchard plots (Fig. 1b) while OH displays linear downward plot (Fig. not shown). The differing trend of OG and OH is reflected in Giles isotherms also. For OG-CPVP system, an isotherm of parabolic shape with an upward tail (in Giles *et al.* terminology¹⁰ L₃ form) was observed and for OH-CPVP an upward straight line plot (C₁ form) was noticed (Fig. 2).

Binding parameters :

For simple linear plots of OH, K and nK were straight-away determined but for complex plots of OG, the linear portion of the plot at high r values was extrapolated to ordinate (marked by dashed line in Fig. 1) and from this they were computed. The correlation coefficient values b , the least square method are obviously low? Table I presents all these values, the maximum percent of sorption and the type of Giles isotherm followed. Temperature variation of K has enabled to calculate thermodynamic parameters (Table 1).

Of the two dyes, OG demonstrates a lesser degree of binding in both the solvent media, as evident from the val-

**Deputed for studies from : Department of Chemistry, T. D. M. N. S. College, T. Kallikulam-627 113, India.

Fig. 1. Scatchard plots (a) in double-distilled water for (1) OG-CPVP and (2) OH-CPVP and (b) in phosphate buffer for OG-CPVP at (1) 30°, (2) 40° and (3) 50°.

Fig. 2. Giles isotherms in double-distilled water for (1) OG-CPVP and (2) OH-CPVP.

ues of K , nK and the percent of sorption (Table 1). A small discrepancy is yet noticeable in the K value which, instead of being lower, is exceptionally high for OG-CPVP in double-distilled water. This may be ascribed to the peculiar mode of binding to be described later. In buffer, however, the difference in degree of binding becomes small, both showing a greater extent of binding. Nevertheless, considerable difference exists in the numerical values of K and nK and in Giles isotherms (L_3 and C_1 respectively). The thermodynamic parameters of the two dye systems also differ. In OG-CPVP complex, both ΔH° and ΔS° are negative, energetic forces predominate with a little entropic forces whereas in OII-CPVP the entropic forces predominate.

Binding mode – Cooperativity in dye binding :

The biphasic plots of OG (Fig. 1a, plot 1 and Fig. 1b) are indicative of mixed cooperativity¹¹ (linear downward–negative and linear upward–positive cooperativity) and the upward linear plot of OH (Fig. 1a, plot 2) a simple positive

Table 1. Binding and thermodynamic parameters

System	Temp. °C	Max. % of sorption	$K \times 10^4, \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (correlation coefficient)	nK $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Giles isotherm
In double-distilled water					
OG-CPVP	Ambient	20	1.24 (0.99)	1.50	L_3
	32				
OH-CPVP	Ambient	34	0.25 (0.69)	23.69	C_1
	32				

		In phosphate buffer			Table-1 (contd.)
OG-CPVP	30	58	0.73 (0.81)	79.33	L_3
	40	52	0.32 (0.65)	62.14	L_3
OH-CPVP	50	50	0.13 (0.27)	53.83	L_3
	30	60	0.98 (0.98)	84.60	C_1
	40	57	0.95 (0.77)	75.52	C_1
	50	54	0.87 (0.84)	74.39	C_1
Thermodynamic parameters in phosphate buffer					
		ΔF° (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (eu)	
OG-CPVP		-2.66	-3.74	-3.62	
OH-CPVP		-5.47	-0.99	+14.98	

cooperativity. Giles isotherms also deduce the same inference (Fig. 2). The L_3 form of OG-CPVP may be considered as to indicate the co-existence of one complete and one partial layers of sorbed dye molecules¹⁰ in adjacent site-regions of CPVP, an arrangement possible only with site-site cooperativity. The C_1 form of OH-CPVP means constant partition isotherm and specifies that a fraction of OH molecules in solution prefers to be in polymer matrix maintaining a constant C_B/C_F ratio. Since OH and CPVP are individually non-polar, sorption of OH from polar aqueous phase to CPVP is facilitated due to like-like interaction involving cooperativity. In OG the two sulfonato groups, by virtue of their position, could interrupt the hydrophobicity of naphthyl and phenylazo moieties and consequently result in an uneven microenvironment around the dye. In OH, however, as the dye has only one sulfonato group at the extreme end position, the molecule remains rather hydrophobic with a uniform microenvironment. These differences in molecular environment of the two dyes may be responsible for their different binding modes with CPVP which is molecularly amphipathic.

Visible spectral studies were performed to provide supportive evidence for the foregoing discussion. Since CPVP is water-insoluble, the linear water-soluble analogue PVP was employed in the place of CPVP for spectral studies. Representative absorption spectra of OG and difference spectra of OH in double-distilled water with PVP are displayed in Fig. 3. OG shows a decrease in absorbance with all the PVP concentrations in the wavelength range 450–500 nm (Fig. 3a). OH, on the other hand, has an opposite trend; in the difference spectra (Fig. 3b) all the plots lie in the $+\Delta A$ side in the entire wavelength range. The course of spectral change also falls in line with the binding trend. When $[PVP] > 0.008 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ {initial [dye]/[PVP] = 16–25}, absorbance of OG reverses its direction in the ordinary spectra. This corresponds to the inflection point ($-$ to $+$ cooperativity)

in the Scatchard plot (Fig. 1a, plot 1). Such spectral changes are attributable to spectroscopically distinguishable complex formations¹² and explain the cooperative mode of binding with the formation of two succeeding complexes in OG-PVP system. With OH, however, since the absorbance change is only in one direction, it indicates only one complex type involving cooperativity. In buffer medium, the spectral changes of OG and OH follow a pathway opposite to those in double-distilled water conforming to the inverse binding trend depicted in the Scatchard plots.

Conclusion :

The remarkable difference in binding characteristics and mode of the two dye-systems studied deciphers that CPVP, a synthetic polymer, is capable of discriminating the molecular features of its associating ligands. In this regard, proteins are well-known¹³ for their pronounced ability to

Fig. 3(a). Absorption spectra of OG (1) and OG-PVP complex (2–5) $[OG] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[PVP] =$ (2) 0.004, (3) 0.008, (4) 0.012 and (5) 0.036 mol dm^{-3} .

Fig. 3(b). Difference absorption spectra of OH-PVP complex. $[OH] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[PVP] = (1) 0.004, (2) 0.012, (3) 0.024$ and $(4) 0.036 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

recognise ligands by forming specific complexes. Our previous work¹² established that PVP can be regarded in equivalence with proteins in so far as ligand binding is concerned. Now CPVP also, unlike proteins with only one type of monomer and water-insolubility, can be considered from the present work to have secured that rank.

Experimental

Materials :

CPVP in the finely powdered grade and PVP ($M_N = 40000$) were obtained from Sigma USA. OG was supplied from S.D. fine-chem, India and OH from Koch-Light, England. Other reagents used were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water (conductivity = $0.14 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) was used in solution preparation. CPVP was purified by washing several times with 0.1 N HCl , 0.1 N NaOH and double-distilled water in order to remove all types of impurities, as checked by UV absorbance of the washings⁷. Dyes and other reagents were used as such.

Methods :

Dye binding to CPVP was studied by batch adsorption technique⁷, employing 20 mg of polymer ($0.018 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in basemole unit) in 10 ml dye solution of concentration $1.0\text{--}10.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ as allowed by Beer-Lambert's law in double-distilled water (experimental solution pH ≈ 5.5) at room temperature ($\approx 32^\circ$) and in 0.05 mol dm^{-3} phosphate buffer ($\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4\text{--Na}_2\text{HPO}_4$) of pH 7.2 at different temperatures, 30, 40 and 50° . Dye concentration in

supernatant was determined by absorbance measurements at their respective λ_{max} values (OG—482 nm; OH—481 nm). The visible absorbance spectra of dye and dye-PVP complex were recorded in matched 1 cm quartz cuvettes (Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer Lambda 3B model).

The binding data were analysed by the Scatchard method⁹ using equation (1),

$$r/C_F = nK - rK \quad (1)$$

where r is the ratio of bound dye concentration (C_B) to $[CPVP]$, C_F , the free unbound [dye], K , the binding constant, n , the number of binding sites per mole of CPVP and nK , the total binding constant. Thermodynamic parameters were determined from the variation of K with temperature using equations (2–4),

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta H^\circ = RT^2 d(\ln K)/dT \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = (\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T \quad (4)$$

where R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature (298 K). The plot of $\ln K$ vs T was a straight line for both OG-CPVP and OH-CPVP systems with correlation coefficients 0.99 and 0.96 respectively. Giles adsorption isotherm¹⁰ was also made use of in analysing binding data. Giles isotherm is a plot of bound ligand concentration (C_B) vs free ligand concentration (C_F) and is qualitative in nature. [The adsorption isotherms comprise four main classes depending on the nature of the slope of the initial portion of the curve : S curves 'Sigmoidal'-cooperative binding; L curves ; 'Langmuir'-simple monolayer binding; H curves 'High affinity'-micellar type binding and C curves 'Constant partition'-partition type binding. Each main class has five sub-classes as S_1, S_2 etc., again depending on the subsequent course of the curve]. Least-square method was adopted for computing binding and thermodynamic parameters.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, India for financial support in the form of minor project and teacher fellowship to (R.M.).

References

1. T. E. Mallouk and J. A. Gavin, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1998, **31**, 209.
2. M. Maruthamuthu and S. Kishore, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 221.
3. M. K. Pal and R. C. Yadav, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 723.

4. P. H. List and U. A. Muazzam, *Drugs Made Ger.*, 1979, **22**, 161 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 203499).
5. E. S. Barabas and C. Adeyeye, *Anal. Profiles Drug Subst. Excipients*, 1996, **24**, 87.
6. M. Maruthamuthu and E. Subramanian, *Polym. Bull.*, 1989, **21**, 505.
7. M. Maruthamuthu and E. Subramanian, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1989, **101**, 259.
8. E. Subramanian, *Indian Drugs*, 1999, **36**, 538.
9. G. Scatchard, *Ann. NY Acad. Sci.*, 1949, **51**, 660.
10. C. H. Giles, T. H. MacEvan, S. N. Nakhwa and D. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3973.
11. J. R. Cann, *Meth. Enzymol., Part F*, 1978, **48**, 299.
12. M. Maruthamuthu and E. Subramanian, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 295.
13. I. M. Klotz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2299.